

Fully Coupled Thermoelastoelectric Simulations of GaN Devices

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Abstract

The continuum equations describing the fully coupled electrical, mechanical and thermal behaviors of GaN devices are presented and illustrated with a variety of examples from RF and power electronics.

Introduction

The burgeoning practical uses of GaN and its alloys for RF, power, lighting, and other applications are making it increasingly vital to be able to simulate the relevant electronic/optical behaviors numerically. For such modeling the strong piezoelectricity of the III-nitrides implies that one must include the coupling to mechanical fields for a full understanding. Moreover, in many applications the devices operate at high temperatures and so this too must often be modeled. Finally, all device situations are inhomogeneous, usually in 2D or even 3D, and therefore a multi-dimensional capability is essential. Toward these ends, we here present the fully coupled theory that describes the thermoelastoelectric behavior of GaN devices, and then illustrate it with a variety of examples.

Governing Equations

Treating all aspects of the III-nitride devices in the continuum limit and assuming electrostatic conditions, the differential equations obeyed inside semiconducting regions are [1]:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = q(N - n) \quad n_{,t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = 0 \quad (1a)$$

$$\mathbf{J} = qn\mu_n \nabla(\varphi_n - \psi) \quad \rho \mathbf{u}_{,tt} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (1b)$$

$$\rho c_p T_{,t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = \eta \mathbf{J} \cdot \nabla(\varphi_n - \psi) \quad (1c)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ and \mathbf{u} are the mechanical stress and displacement fields, \mathbf{q} is the heat flux, η is an efficiency factor accounting for RF power output, and all other symbols have their usual meanings. Assuming linear theory suffices, the thermoelastoelectric constitutive equations (in indicial notation) are:

$$\tau_a = \tau_a^0 + c_{ab} [S_b - \alpha_b (T - T_p)] + e_{ja} \psi_{,j} \quad (2a)$$

$$D_i = P_i^0 + e_{ia} S_a - \epsilon_{ij} \psi_{,j} \quad q_i = -\kappa_{ij} T_{,j} \quad (2b)$$

where a and b range from 1 to 6 and i and j from 1 to 3, ϵ_{ik} , c_{ab} , α_a , κ_{ij} , and e_{ia} are the permittivity, elastic, thermal expansion, thermal conductivity, and piezoelectric tensor coefficients, respectively, P_i^0 is the spontaneous polarization, τ_a^0 is the intrinsic stress, T_p is the baseplate temperature, and

TABLE I.
SELECTED MATERIAL PARAMETERS [2,3].

	GaN	AlN	InN	SiN	SiC
ϵ_{11}	9.5	9	15.3	9.4	9.7
ϵ_{33}	10.4	10.7	15.3	9.4	9.7
c_{11} (GPa)	390	396	223	187	501
c_{12} (GPa)	145	137	115	69	111
c_{13} (GPa)	106	108	92	69	52
c_{33} (GPa)	398	373	224	187	553
c_{44} (GPa)	105	116	48	118	163
e_{15} (C/m ²)	-0.3	-0.48	-0.11	---	---
e_{31} (C/m ²)	-0.33	-0.5	-0.11	---	---
e_{33} (C/m ²)	0.65	1.55	0.95	---	---

$S_a = (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i})/2$ is the linear strain. Many of the coefficient values appear in Table 1 with alloys mostly treated by linear interpolation. The constitutive equations associated with the electron gas are:

$$\varphi_n = \varphi_n(n, T) \quad \mu_n = \mu_n(\psi_{,i}, T) \quad (2c)$$

with the mobility's field dependence providing velocity saturation. Finally, consistent boundary conditions must be specified to impose the bias, introduce external thermal and contact resistances, etc.; all of these are standard in form.

Simulation Methods

Using the above equations one can set up and solve boundary value problems for device situations of interest. The GaN devices studied in this paper (see Fig. 1) are analyzed mostly

Figure 1a. – Schematic of a conventional Ga-face AlGaIn/GaN HEMT.

Figure 1b – Schematic of the scaled N-face AlN/GaN HEMT with self-aligned InGaN contacts from [6].

Figure 2 – Depiction of efficient solution strategy with transport equations solved only in the device region.

Figure 3. – Check of simulated interface charge against results of [2].

in the steady-state limit using the COMSOL package [4] and with the efficiency improved in several ways:

- (i) *Localized transport analysis* (see Fig. 2). Because the Debye length is “small”, the transport equations need be solved only in the relatively small device region near the contacts. The thermomechanics is instead affected by the wafer thickness/device spacing, and so its equations must be solved over a much larger region, but with only a coarse mesh required.
- (ii) *Exploiting 2D nature of most devices*. That most devices are much wider than they are long allows their analysis to be reduced to 2D. Implementation requires that the epitaxial strain in the third dimension be accounted for analytically [1].

A basic verification is of the model and its numerical implementation is shown in Fig. 3 where numerical solutions for interface charge are compared with results from [2].

Applications

A. RF Devices

Simulated I-V curves for the conventional Ga-face AlGaIn/GaN HEMT of Fig. 1a are plotted in Fig. 4; that these curves are much like those measured experimentally (e.g., in [5]) is further verification of the model. One benefit of such simulations is the ability to look inside the device, e.g., under ON-state conditions ($V_G = 0V$, $V_D = 5V$) in Fig. 5a-d. A transient thermal simulation of this device appears in Fig. 6. To

Figure 5 – Simulated (a) electron density, (b) electric field, (c) temperature, and (d) principal stress in an AlGaIn/GaN HEMT in the on-state ($V_D = 5V$).

Figure 4 – Simulated drain characteristics of the AlGaIn/GaN HEMT.

Figure 6 – Simulated temperature transient in the AlGaIn/GaN HEMT.

Figure 7 – Contour plots of (a) the electron density, (b) electric field, and (c) stress of an N-face AlN/GaN HEMT. The drain characteristics are shown in (d).

reach higher frequencies, a variety of scaled designs have recently been developed using Si-like strategies. One example is the N-face AlN/GaN design from the UCSB group [6] shown in Fig. 1b. Solution plots for this device analogous to those of Fig. 5 appear in Fig. 7a-c. Of particular interest are the stresses introduced by the re-grown InGaN/InN S/D contacts. The calculated I-V curves for this enhancement mode device are shown in Fig. 7d. Such an electroelastic analysis would become of even more value for highly scaled devices in which the entire channel would come under the influence of the stress concentrations at the gate corners.

B. Reliability

Conventional AlGaIn/GaN HEMTs (Fig. 1a) are known to fail by apparently mechanical means, with grooves, pits, and cracks often appearing in BT-stressed devices as illustrated in Fig. 8 [7-9]. An intriguing hypothesis about these failures is that they are triggered by piezoelectric stress [9]. Fig. 9a,b shows solutions inside the device in Fig. 1a under high-power conditions with $V_D = 20\text{V}$ and $V_G = 0$. As seen in Fig. 9b, the electric field is quite high at the drain corner of the channel and this will undoubtedly lead to significant electron injection. Similarly, Fig. 9a shows that the channel temperature is very high, and this would surely accelerate any degradation processes. In contrast, the stress levels (Fig. 9b) seem not especially high ($<5\text{GPa}$), and half of the peak stress comes

Figure 8 – (a) TEM [7] and (b) AFM [8] imaging of pits/cracks in BT-stressed AlGaIn/GaN HEMTs.

Figure 9 – Simulated (a) temperature field and (b) electric field, piezoelectric stress, and total stress profiles across the AlGaIn at the source/drain-side corners of the gate under high-power conditions.

Figure 10 – Simulations of a damaged Al-GaN/GaN HEMT with a “crack” at the drain-side corner of the gate and showing (a) the stress concentration effect, the dependence of the peak stress on (b) the crack radius of curvature and (c) the depth of the crack, and (d) the effect of small and large cracks on the drain characteristics.

not from the piezoelectric contribution but from thermal stresses. A further set of simulations in Fig. 10 (for the design of Fig. 1a) shows the stress-concentrating effect of a crack (Fig. 10a), the effects of the crack’s radius of curvature (Fig. 10b) and depth (Fig. 10c) on the level of stress concentration, and the impact that a crack can have on the drain characteristics (Fig. 10d).

Summary

A fully coupled theory of thermoelectroelasticity in III-nitride devices has been presented and illustrated with numerical solutions in several important areas of application.

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